

A pilot public dialogue exploring views towards the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data

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Executive summary

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in sensitive data research is a complex and rapidly emerging area.

There are many public benefits associated with the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data in Trusted Research Environments (TREs). AI models can be much more efficient at analysing very large datasets than humans, and can be more accurate at drawing conclusions from complex data.

However, AI models trained on sensitive data also present new challenges for data privacy. They generally contain a huge amount of data, making it difficult for humans to assess whether a model is disclosive of the privacy of individuals represented in the data they were trained on. They may also be susceptible to hacking – or privacy attacks – to uncover sensitive information, and there are risks of biases and inaccuracies as a result of unrepresentative training data.

Effective governance and regulation are key to mitigating the potential risks to individuals and society from the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data. It is essential that the public, who may be individually or collectively impacted by these risks, are involved in defining what this looks like.

This pilot public dialogue aimed to explore how to effectively engage people without existing knowledge and awareness of the subject matter in conversations about AI in sensitive data research, and uncover their initial views on the topic. Three in-person workshops were held with 22 participants in autumn 2025 in Balsall Heath, an area in Birmingham, England. A mixture of presentations, small group discussions and interactive activities enabled participants to develop their understanding of the subject matter and offer informed views.

Participants expressed optimism about the public benefits of AI trained on sensitive data, but voiced a desire for rigorous data privacy processes, representative training data and clearer lines of consent for data use. Trust was central to discussions, with concern raised about commercial involvement. There was a clear demand that processes to protect sensitive data – including The Five Safes and regulatory requirements – remain fit for purpose in light of the unique challenges posed by AI.

A key challenge throughout the dialogue was maintaining a clear focus on AI trained on sensitive data, with conversations frequently

drifting towards internet-based AI such as ChatGPT. This was likely driven by the significant media discourse around mainstream internet-based AI models at the time the workshops took place, and future work will require concerted efforts to maintain a focus on AI in the context of sensitive data research.

DARE UK will be taking the learnings of this work forward to inform a larger dialogue on the same topic with people from across all four nations of the UK. The aim will be to set out more specific, actionable guidance for the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data in line with public expectations.

Key insights into public expectations and concerns

The findings of this pilot dialogue emphasise some key considerations for the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data in line with public expectations and concerns:

▶ HUMAN INVOLVEMENT

Are humans involved at every stage, or does the proposal demonstrate an over-reliance on AI for decision-making purposes?

▶ INCLUSIVITY

Is the sensitive data being used to train AI models sufficiently representative, or are there gaps or inequalities that could lead to biases or unintended consequences for specific groups or society as a whole?

▶ TRANSPARENCY

Are the end-to-end processes and outputs of projects involving the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data fully transparent?

▶ DATA AND AI MISUSE

Are there appropriate mitigations in place to protect sensitive data and reduce the likelihood that AI could be misused?

▶ PUBLIC AWARENESS

Is there a clear communications plan to inform the public about how their sensitive data is being used to train AI models and/or how AI is being used to analyse their sensitive data?

▶ OVERSIGHT, REGULATION AND ACCOUNTABILITY

Are there processes in place to ensure compliance with the necessary regulations; and are there clear lines of accountability if something goes wrong?

Recommendations for future work

This work highlights key lessons learned for wider public dialogue on the topic led by both DARE UK and others:

1. Adopt a 'funnel' approach to knowledge development

Start with broad, introductory activities to draw out preconceived ideas about AI and allow participants to build foundational understanding before tackling more specific topics.

2. Embed sufficient time for learning and reflection

Given the complexity of the topic, public conversations about data and AI should allow sufficient time for participants to absorb information and reflect on discussions via a multi-phase process.

3. Engage in community settings

Prioritise meeting participants in spaces local to them, rather than expecting them to travel to distant or formal venues. This helps foster trust, reduce perceived power imbalances and create a sense of belonging.

4. Include a variety of interactive activities

Include diverse, hands-on activities that cater to different learning styles and keep participants actively engaged in a technical, fast-moving topic.

5. Illustrate concepts with real world examples

Complex concepts such as Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and machine learning (ML) should be illustrated through practical, real-world examples to help participants connect theoretical discussions to tangible, real-life scenarios.

6. Ensure consistency and accessibility of language

Terminology about AI in the context of sensitive data research should be consistent in conversations with the public. Creation of established plain language messaging will help to support future conversations.

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1/ Definitions

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI): A branch of science that aims to create technology that may perform tasks and make decisions in a way that resembles human intelligence. AI systems can be built in various ways, with the most common current method being machine learning ([UK TRE Glossary](#)).

DE-IDENTIFICATION: The process of removing personal information (details which can directly identify a person such as their name or address) from data, creating 'de-identified data'. While this data no longer contains details that directly identify a person, it can still be linked to identifiable information. This differs from anonymised data, which cannot be linked back to an individual (adapted from [Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative](#)).

MACHINE LEARNING (ML): A subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) is a computer programming technique particularly suited to identifying patterns or rules in large amounts of data. Rather than beginning with a fixed set of rules, an ML program builds up ("learns") a set of likely rules by processing many example datasets (this stage of ML is known as "training"). When the set of likely rules is complete, the ML program can apply them to new datasets

and offer a likely prediction (this stage is known as "inference") ([UK TRE Glossary](#)). "Developing" an ML model (or AI model) refers to both the training of the model and also the development of the software which wraps the trained model, enabling a user to query the model and receive an outcome.

PUBLIC BENEFIT: Public benefit means that there should be some 'net good' accruing to the public; it has both a benefit aspect and a public aspect. The benefit aspect requires the achievement of good, not outweighed by any associated risk. Good is interpreted in a broad and flexible manner and can be direct, indirect, immediate or long-term. Benefit needs to be identifiable, even if it cannot be immediately quantified or measured. The public aspect requires demonstrable benefit to accrue to the public, or a section of the public ([National Data Guardian for Health and Social Care](#)).

PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT AND ENGAGEMENT: Involvement and Engagement are interrelated. Involvement means that activities and research are carried out 'with' or 'by' members of the public, rather than 'to', 'about' or 'for' them. Members of the public are actively involved in the development, running and management of research projects or activities ([National Institute](#)

[for Health and Care Research](#)). Engagement describes the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of an organisation or research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit ([National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement](#)).

SENSITIVE DATA: Sensitive data is data which contains personally identifiable information such as names, addresses and identifying numbers. This data can still be sensitive once it has been de-identified (has had all personal identifiable information removed), particularly if there is potential for re-identification when used with other data. Commercial data such as retail information, business details or confidential product details may also be considered sensitive when used for research ([DARE UK](#)).

SENSITIVE DATA RESEARCH: The process of collecting, analysing and interpreting sensitive data to help answer questions, identify patterns or support decision making. Sensitive data research can be carried out across various sectors, from healthcare to business. It involves applying strict safeguards, governance and ethical practices to ensure data is used legally, safely and responsibly

for research in the public benefit (adapted from [Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative](#) definition of 'Data Research').

THE FIVE SAFES: The Five Safes, which include Safe Data, Safe Settings, Safe People, Safe Projects and Safe Outputs, is a set of principles which enable data services to provide safe research access to data. The framework originated from the ONS and was developed by them and other data providers in the 2010s. The framework has become best practice in data protection whilst fulfilling the demands of open science and transparency ([UK Data Service](#)).

TRUSTED RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT (TRE): A highly secure digital environment that provides access to sensitive data for analysis by approved researchers. A series of strict security measures protect the privacy of the people the data is about, significantly reducing the potential for data misuse or the possibility of re-identification of de-identified data. This enables researchers to securely analyse data as part of important projects to inform policy and practice and improve lives ([DARE UK](#)). Other commonly used terms for equivalent environments in the UK include 'Safe Haven' and 'Secure Data Environment'.

2/ Introduction

DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) is a programme which aims to establish a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) where approved researchers can efficiently access and analyse sensitive data to advance research for public benefit. By co-creating this network with relevant communities and the public, we aim to enhance research while maintaining the security and confidentiality of sensitive data.

DARE UK was established with the vision for all research and innovation to benefit from seamless, secure use of diverse sensitive data at a pace, efficiency and scale that revolutionises research productivity and accelerates research to deliver public good. DARE UK's mission is to put the UK at the forefront of sensitive data research and innovation by assembling the tools, technologies and standards needed to streamline secure data linkage and use.

DARE UK is funded by [UK Research and Innovation](#), the UK's largest public funder of research, and is led by [Health Data Research UK \(HDR UK\)](#) and [ADR UK \(Administrative Data Research UK\)](#).

Artificial Intelligence in sensitive data research

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in sensitive data research is a complex and rapidly emerging area. In the context of TREs, AI usually refers to machine learning (ML). An ML model (or 'AI model') trained using sensitive data held in a TRE can help identify patterns or draw conclusions from other, similar data. A model might be trained on medical images to identify signs of breast cancer in mammograms,¹ for example; or trained on satellite images to help with understanding land coverage and tackling climate change impacts.²

In Phase 2 of the DARE UK programme, which runs from August 2024 to March 2027, several projects and Community Groups have a focus on AI. This includes, for example, the training of AI models using sensitive data in TREs and their safe 'release' from the TRE³; and how to enable access to AI supercomputers for researchers training AI models in TREs⁴.

There are many benefits associated with the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data. AI models can be much more efficient at analysing very large datasets than humans, can save time by automating processes, and can be more accurate at drawing conclusions from complex data, to name a few. This represents significant potential for public benefit. However, AI models trained on sensitive data also present new challenges for data privacy, particularly when considering their release from a TRE. These models generally contain a huge amount of data, making them not easily 'readable' by humans. This means it is difficult for humans to assess whether an AI model is disclosive of the privacy of individuals represented in the data they were trained on. AI models may also be susceptible to hacking – or privacy attacks – to uncover sensitive information used to train them, and potentially even re-identify it (Jefferson et al. 2022, Ritchie et al. 2023, Hotchkiss et al. 2024, Niu et al. 2024, Information Commissioner's Office [1]).

In addition, there are risks of biases and inaccuracies in AI models as a result of unrepresentative training data, which could lead to

discrimination against certain groups (Information Commissioner's Office [2]). If the data used to train an AI model is not representative of everybody in society – for example, different ethnicities, genders and ages – then it is reasonable to assume that the outputs of the model could not be representative. This may have adverse effects for individuals or groups if decisions are made for or about them based on AI outputs which are not relevant to their characteristics.

Effective governance and regulation are key to mitigating the potential risks to individuals and society from the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data. And the 2025 Public Attitudes to Science survey, commissioned by UK Research and Innovation, found that making people feel more informed about AI or other controversial technologies may not, on its own, build public trust or allay concerns (Ipsos 2026). It is therefore essential that the public, who may be individually or collectively impacted by the risks associated with AI, are involved in defining what AI governance and regulation looks like.

¹ BBC News '[NHS AI test spots tiny cancers missed by doctors](#)' 21.03.2024

² University of Aberdeen '[AI model developed to unlock the potential of satellite imagery for land cover mapping](#)' 20.06.2025

³ **VISTA**: Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI; **PANORAMA**: Pan-North Data Research Advancements for Multi-Domain Access and Analysis; **SAFETEXT**: Community-led Protocols for the Safe and Responsible Use of De-identified and Synthetic Healthcare Text for AI Development; **SDC-REBOOT**: Statistical Disclosure Control – Reducing Barriers to Outputs from TREs

⁴ **FRIDGE**: Federated Research Infrastructure by Data Governance Extension

Inclusive involvement

In 2022, as part of Phase 1 of the DARE UK programme, we carried out a public dialogue with 44 members of the public from across the UK to explore views towards how the UK's data research infrastructure could work in a more joined-up, efficient and trustworthy way.

A key recommendation was...

“Public involvement and engagement should be meaningful and inclusive”.

Specifically...

“Proactive and targeted outreach should be used to increase inclusion of neglected groups and make involvement and engagement more representative of the UK...”

And...

“Public involvement and engagement activities should equip members of the public with sufficient understanding to take part in genuine conversations about data research processes and offer informed input”.

(Harkness et al. 2022).

Additionally, the Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative (PEDRI) has developed seven Good Practice Standards⁵ to address key barriers to effective public involvement and engagement in data research. Of particular relevance to this work, these include:

- 1 EQUITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION:**
The fair and balanced inclusion of people with different backgrounds, experiences, and identities in research projects or initiatives involving data about people and communities.
- 2 DATA LITERACY AND TRAINING:**
The ability to read, understand, and communicate data – known as data literacy – empowers people to engage in data research and statistics, which can often be complex and challenging to navigate.

To ensure meaningful public involvement that champions equity, diversity and inclusion, it is essential that, as a sector, we engage with the wider public in our ongoing work, and not only with those with existing knowledge of and involvement in it. This is particularly important for rapidly evolving topics such as AI, and embedding sufficient time for training and knowledge development is essential for effective public conversations on these topics.

⁵Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative. [Our Good Practice Standards](#). Accessed 20.02.2026

Previous literature

A body of recent UK research has explored public views towards the rise of AI in general. Previous studies have also explored views towards AI trained on sensitive data with small groups or with a distinct focus on health data.

Recent research exploring public views towards AI in general (not specific to sensitive data) has been largely survey-based and has found mixed sentiments. The most recent data and AI public attitudes tracker survey by the UK Government has reported growing public trust and improved optimism about data practices. However, public perceptions of AI are dominated by concerns, and there is a knowledge gap on how AI is trained (Department for Science, Innovation and Technology 2024).

Joint work by the Ada Lovelace Institute and the Alan Turing Institute found that views towards AI vary between different groups in society (Modhvadia et al. 2025). They found people on lower incomes to consistently report lower net benefit scores across AI technologies compared to people on higher incomes. Different ethnic groups were also found to report differing levels of concern about AI – while 39% of the general population expressed concern about the use of facial recognition in policing, this rose to over half

among Black (57%) and Asian (52%) people. These findings demonstrate that the public cannot be treated as homogeneous in conversations about AI.

Previous studies have also explored public views towards the use of health data for AI research and the development of AI systems in healthcare. They have found that most people are comfortable with their health data being used to develop AI, on the condition that existing concerns about data privacy, the representativeness of training data and commercial involvement are addressed. Trust and transparency have been found to be key to public comfort, and consent is a clear area of concern, with an apparent desire for greater individual choice over how data is used to develop AI (Aggarwal et al. 2021, Ipsos 2022, Binesmael et al. 2024, Kuo et al. 2026).

In terms of the perceived public benefits of AI, participants of these studies have referenced improved access to healthcare, improved shopping experiences, increased access to learning or

education, earlier warning of new medical conditions, help in detecting welfare fraud, and improvements related to speed and efficiency. However, perceived negative impacts have included data security and the use of personal data without consent, difficulty in telling whether news or information are fake, increased cybercrime, an overreliance on technology over professional judgement, errors, and a lack of transparency in decision-making. The need for independent regulation of AI, and a lack of trust in the way commercial organisations manage and use data and AI, have also been recurring themes.

Previous and ongoing DARE UK-funded projects and initiatives exploring AI have involved members of the public to help shape their work. The GRAIMatter project⁶ held a series of five workshops with eight members of the public with an interest in health data research to advise the development of a draft set

of recommendations to guard against the additional risks when disclosing trained AI models from TREs. Participants expressed concern about the privacy risks associated with training AI on sensitive data and recommended that public representatives should be involved in data governance and ethics approvals processes. They also stressed that the use of data for training AI models and the controls on the models should be publicly visible through data use registers (Jefferson et al. 2022).

The AI Risk Evaluation Working Group⁷ sought to develop risk assessment methodologies, governance, and training to enable the safe release of AI models from TREs. A public workshop with participants with varying existing understanding of sensitive data research explored views towards AI models in healthcare and concerns with data usage in AI research. Participants recognised the potential benefits of

AI for healthcare, including increased speed of diagnosis and improved treatment, and a majority (82%) were happy for their data to be used to train an AI model within a TRE. However, they felt there was not currently enough informed consent for the use of health data to train AI. They were also concerned that some groups were more at risk than others from the unique security challenges posed by AI, such as those with a rare condition or from an ethnic minority background. A need for greater regulation of AI was a key theme, and participants felt the public should continue to be involved in decision-making processes to ensure AI models are being developed in the public good (Hotchkiss et al. 2024).

To our knowledge, however, there has been no widescale public dialogue with people from across the UK who are unfamiliar with sensitive data research to explore their views on the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data, particularly beyond the scope of health. In addition, public discourse around AI has shifted significantly over recent years, largely driven by the release of ChatGPT in November 2022 and the rapid rise of mainstream, internet-based AI models since then. A greater level of public awareness and opinion about AI in general is therefore expected to have had an impact on people's pre-conceived ideas about, and views towards, AI in the context of sensitive data research.

As AI technology and public discourse continue to rapidly evolve, there is a clear need for DARE UK, and the sensitive data research sector as a whole, to gain a deeper and ongoing understanding of attitudes of the UK public towards the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data. This will help to ensure AI trained on sensitive data is used in a trustworthy way. This pilot public dialogue represents a first step in filling this gap.

⁶ DARE UK. [GRAIMATTER: Guidelines and Resources for Artificial Intelligence Model Access from Trusted Research Environments](#). Accessed 20.02.2026

⁷ DARE UK. [AI Risk Evaluation Working Group](#). Accessed 20.02.2026

3/ Purpose and objectives

This pilot public dialogue aimed to test messaging and approaches to knowledge development for a new, complex technical topic with a cross-section of the public in England who had limited prior knowledge of sensitive data research and AI.

The aim was to identify **key learnings** and lay the foundations for a **larger, UK-wide public dialogue** on the topic led by DARE UK in partnership with other organisations across the sector.

OBJECTIVES OF THE DIALOGUE

- 1** Explore how to effectively engage with people without existing knowledge and awareness of the subject matter in conversations about AI in sensitive data research, with a focus on:
 - a) Learning and knowledge development for a complex technical topic without existing established public messaging.
 - b) Achieving and maintaining active participation throughout a multi-phase process.
 - c) Achieving an atmosphere where participants feel confident to express their views and concerns openly and honestly.

- 2** Explore people's concerns, expectations and assumptions about the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data, including views towards:
 - a) The training of AI models using sensitive data in TREs.
 - b) The use of AI models trained on sensitive data to support decision making, for example in clinical or policing settings.

4/ Methodology

Public dialogue is a proven method for providing “in-depth insight into public views, concerns and aspirations on issues relating to science and technology. A diverse group of the public explore an issue in detail, so that they can contribute informed opinions and ideas about it.”⁸

To enable inclusive involvement, a mixture of presentations and group activities and discussions give participants the opportunity to explore the topic in detail, develop their understanding of key concepts, and share perspectives in a dynamic and reflective way. Typically, this occurs over a series of workshops where participants have the opportunity to learn from and engage with specialists about the key issues under discussion.⁹ This is important for exploring complex technical topics with a group with limited existing understanding of the subject matter, to enable effective discussions.

Nevertheless, as emphasised by the Royal Society of Arts, *“the time and facilitation needed to explore complex topics in adequate depth can prove costly and slow, and [prevailing] approaches routinely struggle to engage or empower voices that have long been marginalised in the policymaking process”*.¹⁰

Due to the rapid technological advancement of AI trained on sensitive data, the limited existing literature on public attitudes towards and limited established public messaging on the topic, as well as the need for inclusive involvement, an initial pilot was therefore considered a key first step in exploring public views in an effective way.

The aim was to test and refine a multi-phase workshop approach geared towards enabling effective public conversations on the topic, whilst also identifying key challenges and how to overcome them, before scaling to a larger, UK-wide effort.

⁸ Sciencewise. [What is public dialogue?](#) Accessed 20.02.2026

⁹ Involve. [Public Dialogue](#). Accessed 20.02.2026

¹⁰ Royal Society of Arts (2025). [Rethinking Public Dialogue: Learning from experimental pilots](#)

The workshop process

A multi-phase process featured three four-hour, in-person workshops held with the same group of people.

Aligned to the need for effective data literacy and training, the goal was to provide participants with sufficient time to develop understanding of the subject matter, with time built in for reflection between sessions. It also served to avoid information overload and allow flexibility to participants for other commitments during the day.

The workshops were held on the same weekday and time across a period of three weeks in October and November 2025. A separate, two-hour online workshop was held with additional participants who were recruited following the first in-person workshop.

An independent plenary facilitator was appointed to lead the workshops to maintain neutrality and offer an unbiased perspective to broader discussions, as well as support with maintaining accessible and plain English language throughout. Small group discussions and activities were limited to six to eight participants and were led by a facilitator at each table, supported by a discussion guide with pre-defined prompts. Agendas for each workshop can be found in Appendix 1.

The questions explored during facilitated group activities and discussions can be seen in Table 1. In line with the exploratory nature of this work, the purpose was not to seek consensus on these questions among participants, nor to illicit views from participants on every question, but rather to use the questions to tease out participants' understanding of and views towards key topics. Due to the discursive nature of the workshops, not all questions would have been asked exactly as written, and not all groups would have been prompted with all questions listed.

Table 1: Key questions explored in the workshops

Theme	Questions
Balancing benefit and risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What do you feel are the main benefits and risks of training AI models on sensitive data in TREs? Do the benefits outweigh the risks? ▶ What do you feel are the main benefits and risks of releasing AI models trained on sensitive data from TREs? Do the benefits outweigh the risks?
Safeguards and oversight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What safeguards are essential for AI models to be safely released from TREs? ▶ What mitigations or safeguards need to be in place to reduce the likelihood of negative impacts of AI models trained on sensitive data on individuals or society? ▶ Should humans always be involved in the use of AI models trained on sensitive data? Are there any scenarios where humans don't need to be involved?
Governance and accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What should be included in sensitive data and AI regulations? ▶ Who should be involved in decision-making about the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data? ▶ If something goes wrong, who should be accountable and what sanctions should there be?
Comfort and trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ How would you feel about your sensitive data being used to train an AI model in a TRE? ▶ How do you feel about the analysis of sensitive data in TREs using AI models? ▶ Do you have any concerns about sensitive data being used to train AI models in TREs?
Awareness and understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ How have your views on sensitive data and AI changed over the course of the workshops? ▶ Do you think the workshops have increased your awareness and understanding of sensitive data and AI?
Engagement and inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Did you feel able to express your views during the workshops? ▶ What helped or hindered your participation? ▶ What advice would you give us if we were to run these workshops again?

Figure 1: Examples of AI model use case cards discussed during workshop 2

Mapping gangs through tattoo image classification

What?

An AI model that can identify tattoos associated with gangs. When shown an image of a tattoo, the model predicts what, if any, gang the owner of the tattoo is associated with.

How?

The model is trained using a database of tattoo images that are known to be affiliated with gangs. It contains over 1.3 million photos of tattoos taken by police officers and prison guards during arrests, surveillance operations and inmate interviews.

Source: Ada Lovelace Institute (2022).
Looking Before We Leap

An app to support early detection of skin cancer

What?

An AI model that can predict the presence of skin cancer based on photos and symptom notes uploaded to an app on your phone.

How?

The model is trained on existing images of skin lesions (areas of skin that are different from the skin around them), as well as clinical notes, to be able to predict whether a person should see their GP.

Source: Watson, M. (2025). 'Multimodal skin cancer detection: Leveraging free text and images' HDR UK Conference 2025.

Participants

A place-based approach was used for recruiting participants, with a focus on the Balsall Heath area of Birmingham, England. By locating the workshops in a local community centre, the intention was to ensure the events were as accessible as possible for attendees, increasing the likelihood of participation by making attendance easy and comfortable.

B12 Urban Village Hall

In line with the importance of inclusive involvement as discussed above, recruiting people from a diversity of different backgrounds, experiences and identities was crucial to ensure a broad range of perspectives were included in the discussions, particularly those who are often underrepresented in research.¹¹ Balsall Heath was therefore selected based on its relative diversity compared to the city and country as a whole. This includes a higher proportion of residents from ethnic minority backgrounds, including Pakistani, Black African and Black Caribbean communities; a higher proportion of young people; and a diverse spread of qualification levels and occupations.¹² Balsall Heath also has vibrant community activity, with spaces such as the B12 Urban Village Hall, where the workshops were held, based within the heart of the community.

Recruitment was led by [Birmingham Voluntary Service Council](#), who worked with local community researchers – who are based in and passionate about their local community – to carry out ‘on-the-ground’ recruitment to encourage individuals within their communities to participate. Six community researchers carried out one full day of recruitment each, distributing digital and paper flyers about the workshops to support conversations with potential participants online and in-person in community settings in the Balsall Heath area. By engaging with a variety of different community groups – including groups related to, for example, faith, gender and age – a diverse participation could be reached.

In the first instance, 18 public members were recruited and 17 attended the first workshop. A further five participants were recruited ahead of the second workshop to increase the gender diversity of the group. All newly recruited participants attended an online induction to catch them up on the learning and discussions from workshop 1 in advance of workshop 2. For the second and third workshops, 22 attended.

All participants were offered a £100 shopping voucher for attending each in-person workshop to recognise their valuable time and input. Those who attended the online induction were offered a £50 voucher for their involvement in the two-hour session.

In the third workshop, all participants were invited to complete an optional, anonymous demographic information form provided in online and paper format. 19 participants responded to the form. An overview of the demographic characteristics of those who responded can be seen on the next page, and the full data can be found in Appendix 2.

¹¹ University of Oxford Medical Sciences Division. [Involving people from diverse and under-represented groups](#). Accessed 20.02.2026

¹² Birmingham City Council. [Balsall Heath West Factsheet](#). Accessed 20.02.2026

Who took part?

Total participants

Female

14
73.7%

Male

4
21%

Self-described gender

1
5.3%

Disability

Yes

3
15.8%

No

13
68.4%

Prefer not to say

3
15.8%

Age

24 and under	1 (5.3%)
25-34	1 (5.3%)
35-44	7 (36.7%)
45-54	6 (31.6%)
55-64	2 (10.6%)
65-74	2 (10.6%)

Ethnicity

Asian or Asian British – Bangladeshi	2 (10.6%)
Asian or Asian British – Chinese	1 (5.3%)
Asian or Asian British – Pakistani	3 (15.8%)
Black or Black British – African	2 (10.6%)
Black or Black British – Caribbean	1 (5.3%)
Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups - White and Black African	1 (5.3%)
Any other mixed or multiple ethnic groups	1 (5.3%)
White – English, Welsh, Scottish, Northern Irish or British	7 (36.7%)

*Of the 22 participants that took part, 19 responded to the demographic survey. The figures on this page therefore represent the characteristics of the 19 participants who responded.

Steering group

Throughout the design and delivery of the dialogue, the project was guided by input from a Steering Group.

The Group was made up of six individuals, including professionals working in public involvement and engagement in data research, and public contributors involved in existing DARE UK programmes of work.

The Group helped shape the workshop design, reviewed workshop materials, supported workshop delivery and collaborated to draw out key learnings and refine the process following each workshop. They helped to ensure the dialogue was informed by good practice, inclusive approaches and the needs of the wider data research sector. The two public contributors provided a valuable public perspective in helping shape the approach and workshop materials. The Group met 11 times throughout the duration of the project. A list of Steering Group members can be found in Appendix 3.

Analysis

Notes taken by notetakers and facilitators during workshop discussions and activities were used to capture participant views.

Ongoing thematic analysis was conducted throughout the process, with notes from each workshop iteratively reviewed to identify patterns and draw out emergent themes. This process was supported by facilitator and notetaker debriefs at Steering Group meetings following each event.

At the beginning of the third workshop, the plenary facilitator presented emerging themes identified from the discussions in workshops 1 and 2 back to participants. Table discussions addressed the accuracy of the themes presented and drew out any additional themes that may have been missed.

Following the workshops, all workshop notes and other outputs (group posters and participant sticky notes), as well as Steering Group meeting minutes, were reviewed and synthesised to reinforce common themes and identify recommendations for future public dialogue.

5/ Findings

Views towards the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data

From the beginning of the workshops, participants expressed recognition that there could be a public benefit from AI in general (not specific to sensitive data), such as providing quicker and easier access to information.

There was also a general acknowledgement that the use of AI was inevitable, and that people are increasingly using it in everyday life without even realising it, though there were concerns about the growing prevalence of AI in society.

With regards to sensitive data, participants' sense of reassurance in the security processes in place to protect data, and the benefits of AI trained on sensitive data, grew as a result of their participation in the workshops. Upon learning about the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data, there was acknowledgment that AI could be more efficient and accurate than humans for analysing and drawing conclusions from data.

By the end of the workshops, there was overwhelming support for AI trained on sensitive data, based on a view that it could result in significant public benefit.

However, this support was conditional upon a number of assurances, as outlined in the sections below. The central theme to arise in discussions was that of trust: participants wanted to see a demonstration of trustworthiness from those developing and using AI trained on sensitive data. They particularly wanted reassurance that AI is working in the public benefit and not against it. In the poster activity in workshop 2, one group placed trust at the centre of their poster,

explaining "Trust is central to everything". One participant commented, "Data misuse and misrepresentation erode trust", and there was consensus in the room that trust must be earned and maintained, and can easily be lost.

"Data misuse and misrepresentation erode trust".

Workshop participant

AI IS A TOOL, NOT A SOLUTION: HUMANS SHOULD ALWAYS BE INVOLVED

There was a clear feeling among workshop participants that AI is only a tool, and humans should always be involved. There was general consensus that AI cannot be fully relied upon, and that final decisions should ultimately always remain in the hands of humans.

Participants questioned the accuracy of AI, and expressed that it doesn't tell the full story and is "only a lead". In the poster activity in workshop 2, one group highlighted that they did not want to be "reduced to a chip or a number". The output of an AI tool may not give the full picture, and further investigation needs to take place before decisions are made.

There was also a feeling that the outputs of AI models could lead to stigma or stereotyping of certain groups, and in turn discrimination. It was felt that human involvement was important for reducing the likelihood of this by ensuring AI outputs are not taken at face value, and that the full context is always considered.

INCLUSIVE AI RELIES ON INCLUSIVE DATA

There was clear consensus among the group that, for AI models to benefit everyone, they need to be trained on data that represents everyone. One

participant commented, "The AI is only as good as the data". There was agreement that, if the data AI models have been trained on is not inclusive, the outputs of the models themselves cannot be inclusive, raising the risk of biases and inaccuracies. Another participant commented, "AI could replicate the problems it seeks to fix".

Inclusive training data was seen as particularly crucial for preventing adverse effects of biased AI in use in operational settings (for example, clinical or policing settings), particularly for minority groups who are historically underrepresented in data. Participants expressed the need for AI models used in dermatology, for example, to be trained on data representing all skin tones to ensure accuracy for all ethnicities.

They also questioned data collection methods, particularly in relation to free-text (for example, written notes taken by carers, doctors or teachers for inclusion in an individual's record). They questioned if data is being collected in the same

"The AI is only as good as the data".

Workshop participant

way by different individuals or organisations, and if not, if this may lead to inaccuracies when it is used to train AI models. This emphasises the need for robust harmonisation of data used to train AI models.

Participants also expressed that humans may be contributing to biases in AI models during the training phase. One participant commented, "If data input is done by humans, won't the output be determined by this?". This highlights concerns about not only the quality and representativeness of training data, but also about the influence of researchers training the models. This emphasises the importance of transparency, accountability and oversight in the training and release of AI models from TREs.

TRANSPARENCY AND PUBLIC AWARENESS

Participants noted the importance of transparency in how and why AI is trained and used on sensitive data, and by who. They wanted to see decision-making processes, such as those of data access committees, published publicly, for example on TRE websites. Transparency was seen as closely linked to accountability, with clear information about end-to-end processes reducing the potential for "blame games" when something goes wrong. They also wanted to see public information about the accuracy of AI models, and about the representativeness of the data used to train them.

Participants wanted information about the outcomes of sensitive data and AI research to be easily accessible. One participant said there should be a “*place where we can go*” to follow the research, and information should be in plain language. Others raised concerns about the “cult of the expert”, expressing a feeling that those working in data research and the wider science field “*speak a different language*”, and better public information was considered key to bridging this gap. In addition, some said that all research publications developed using public sector data should be open access, and not behind a pay wall.

Some participants reflected how media stories had fuelled their concerns about AI and sensitive data. A recurring feeling among many was that, in general, people do not seem to know much about data and AI. There was a feeling that the public should receive better communication about the

**“AI is a smoke screen...
It’s not about the AI –
it’s about the data and
protecting the data.”**

Workshop participant

topic to support them in making informed decisions about their data and enable more critical assessment of stories in the media.

As the workshops largely eased participants’ initial concerns about the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data, they felt that broader public understanding would reduce reluctance to share information with public services due to fears about how it might be used. Reference was made to historically underrepresented or vulnerable groups, such as ethnic minorities and refugees. One suggestion was to embed data and AI education in school curriculums to help to support greater knowledge and understanding from a young age.

Some attendees also queried the extent to which people working within government have sufficient knowledge about sensitive data and AI and are able to make informed decisions about them. It was felt that those working in government should also be better informed.

DATA PRIVACY AND AI MISUSE

Overall, workshop participants were largely reassured by the explanations given about TRES and The Five Safes, particularly regarding the de-identification of data, and did not express significant concern about risks to personal privacy from the use of sensitive data within TRES. There

**“Any invention for good
can be misused”.**

Workshop participant

was a feeling that, when used to train AI models, sensitive data should continue to be treated with a similar level of care. One participant commented: “*AI is a smoke screen... It’s not about the AI – it’s about the data and protecting the data.*”

Participants expressed concern about the potential for misuse of AI trained on sensitive data, and the impact this could have upon particular groups or society as a whole. They could acknowledge the benefits to society of training AI models on sensitive data, but queried “*which parts of society would benefit?*” In particular, there were concerns about “*bad actors*”, especially politicians and private companies who might seek to use AI trained on sensitive data for reasons other than its intended purpose. This might be to further their own political or commercial agendas or target vulnerable groups, such as for marketing purposes; or to try and find out information about the people the AI model was trained upon. One participant commented, “*Any invention for good can be misused*”.

These findings highlight the ongoing importance of The Five Safes principles in the context of AI, particularly Safe People. Trust is key to guarding against the misuse of AI trained on sensitive data as much as possible.

EFFECTIVE OVERSIGHT, REGULATION AND ACCOUNTABILITY

Oversight, regulation and accountability were recurring themes across all three workshops. Participants felt it is important that existing oversight and regulation surrounding sensitive data research are reviewed and updated to account for AI, and that they are properly enforced.

Although they understood that consent is not always required for the use of sensitive data in research, some participants felt that, where consent is required, current processes should be updated to include explicit consent for use in training AI. One suggestion was to have separate options or checkboxes to consent to the use of data in traditional research versus AI research and development, so that individuals have more agency over what their data is used for. There was also a suggestion that consent should be renewed on a regular basis to ensure new developments in research are accounted for.

There was strong support for “*independent panels*” to make decisions about sensitive data in the context of AI. Suggested membership of these panels included technical experts, AI researchers and members of the public and/or community leaders. There was a feeling that government should be involved, but that this should be carefully managed to reduce the possibility of political bias. Participants expressed a strong feeling that all involved should be heavily vetted to prevent “*bad actors*” from gaining influence. There was agreement that these panels should be closely regulated by an external party, though there was not a clear sense of who should be responsible for this. Participants also agreed that there should be oversight and constant monitoring of the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data.

For any oversight or scrutiny body to be effective, participants felt it would need to have ‘teeth’ to ensure any breaches of rules or guidelines are appropriately sanctioned. There was frequent reiteration of the need for clear lines of accountability and sanctions “*if something goes wrong*”. When discussing what “*goes wrong*” means in the context of sensitive data and AI, participants referred to data breaches affecting people’s privacy, unintended consequences for particular groups, or AI being used to further government or commercial agendas that are not in the public interest.

It was felt there should be accountability for everyone involved in the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data, including those who share the data (e.g. data controllers) and those who use the data (e.g. researchers/developers), although government and commercial organisations were viewed as needing to hold more accountability than others. It was felt there should be sanctions appropriate to the severity of the issue, and that these could include job losses, fines and imprisonment. There should be compensation for people affected, for example if their privacy is compromised or their lives are otherwise negatively impacted in some way.

When considering DARE UK’s broader mission of establishing a connected UK network of TREs, participants could see the benefits of ‘joining up’ TREs, but also expressed concern about putting all TREs under the control of a single entity or organisation. It was felt that it would be safer for control of data to be localised, but for regulation and independent oversight to be harmonised.

Key insights from the workshop process

Based on both participant feedback and reflections from facilitators and notetakers, the following themes focus on key learnings from a workshop series which sought to engage a previously uninformed group with a new, complex and highly technical topic.

WORKSHOP PARTICIPATION

A number of factors influenced participants' decision to get involved in the workshops and remain engaged for the duration of the process. With regards to the scheduling of the workshops, most considered weekdays to be easier for attendance. Others raised concerns that weekday events may have excluded individuals in full-time work or education, whilst also acknowledging that weekends may be reserved for family or rest time for many who work or study during the week. Participants recommended tailoring the timing of sessions to the target audience, such as weekends for full-time students.

Several participants said they initially felt sceptical about taking part in the workshops, as some received the recruitment advert through WhatsApp and thought it might be a scam. They suggested having easily accessible information about the workshops on a public website would help to validate authenticity. Participants expressed that the workshops produced a comfortable, safe, and welcoming atmosphere that encouraged them to participate actively, with one participant reflecting, "I felt at ease to voice my opinions". Some suggested that emphasising the

informal, interactive and friendly nature of sessions in recruitment materials might help encourage attendance, expressing that they found the workshops "more fun than expected".

Some participants highlighted that the location of the workshops in a familiar, community-based venue was a decisive factor in their decision to take part, noting that they would not have joined if they had to travel to a more formal venue in the city centre. It was felt that the choice of venue helped create a familiar and welcoming atmosphere that also reduced perceived power imbalances. Participants also found that all being from the same local area provided a common ground, which helped to facilitate initial connections and build trust.

"I felt at ease to voice my opinions".

Workshop participant

WORKSHOP DESIGN

Participants generally appreciated the overall schedule of the workshops, including their frequency, length, the number of breaks, and the weekly cadence rather than multiple sessions within a single week. This allowed them time to reflect and build knowledge progressively. There was general agreement that short, one-off workshops would be inadequate for effective engagement on such a complex topic.

While participants valued variation in presentations and types of activity during the workshops, a strong preference was expressed for more interactive and hands-on activities to maintain focus, enable creative thinking, move around the room and interact with other participants. A group poster collage activity in workshop 2, for example, was considered particularly engaging. Some participants expressed that interactive activities were especially helpful for getting to know other people in the room and would serve well as initial ice-breaker activities. Others expressed that these types of activities were better suited to later stages of the process when participants had got to know each other better and felt more comfortable working together.

Participants commented on the length and structure of presentations and activities, with a preference for shorter presentations and more time for discussion. Suggestions included breaking presentations into shorter sections with Q&A intervals to allow for greater interaction. For activities involving pre-prepared materials for participants to discuss, it was felt that ample time should be provided to be able to explore the materials in sufficient depth.

At the outset of the workshops, the group co-created a 'Ways of Working' poster, which gave participants ownership of how they would work together. They felt revisiting these guidelines at the start of each session demonstrated commitment and helped maintain a respectful and productive environment. To support anonymous feedback, participants were also encouraged to add comments to a WIFLE (What I Feel Like Expressing) Box and online WIFLE Board. While they appreciated the idea, engagement was minimal. Facilitators observed that most participants seemed comfortable sharing concerns openly within the group or in one-on-one conversations, further emphasising the importance of creating an open and safe space for honest dialogue.

6/ Conclusions

The complexity of this topic underscores the need for dedicated time and resources to build knowledge and understanding and enable effective public input.

A key challenge during the workshops was maintaining a clear focus on sensitive data and TREs in discussions about AI, with conversations frequently drifting towards internet-based AI such as ChatGPT, Siri and Alexa. Both facilitators and participants were cognisant of the challenge, which was likely driven by the significant media discourse around mainstream internet-based AI models at the time the workshops took place. Future work will require concerted efforts to maintain a focus on AI in the context of sensitive data research, whilst also preserving the open, discursive nature of discussions which characterises effective public dialogue. The recommendations provided in the next section offer input on how to achieve this.

This work found a similar mix of optimism and concern as has been highlighted in previous literature. As has been highlighted in previous

work exploring public attitudes to sensitive health data and AI, there was a similar desire for rigorous data privacy processes, representativeness of AI training data and clearer lines of consent, and concern about commercial involvement. The findings also resonate with those of previous DARE UK-funded work, which also highlighted concerns about consent (AI Risk Evaluation Working Group), as well as a call for ongoing public involvement in decision-making processes (both GRAIMatter and AI Risk Evaluation Working Group).

This work also highlighted unique considerations for public benefit as well as data security, bias and misuse where sensitive data is involved in the training and use of AI. Notably, there was concern about the potential misuse of AI trained on sensitive data, and the implications this could have on all or some of society. This appeared to be

driven by a greater perceived potential for sensitive data misuse enabled by AI technologies compared to traditional data research. This demonstrates a clear demand that processes to protect sensitive data – including The Five Safes and regulatory requirements – remain fit for purpose in light of the unique challenges posed by AI.

There is also a clear need to raise public awareness about how AI trained on sensitive data is developed and used to offer reassurance and enable informed decision-making. This will ultimately improve the inclusiveness of data and therefore AI by increasing trust in public services and reducing opt outs where relevant. This relies on the creation of sector-wide, established plain language messaging to support both communications and future public conversations on the topic.

To meet public expectations and uphold ethical standards, AI researchers and decision-makers (including data custodians and data access review panels) should consider the themes raised in this report when assessing proposals to train, use and release AI models from TREs.

HUMAN INVOLVEMENT

Are humans involved at every stage, or does the proposal demonstrate an over-reliance on AI for decision-making purposes?

INCLUSIVITY

Is the sensitive data being used to train AI models sufficiently representative, or are there gaps or inequalities that could lead to biases or unintended consequences for specific groups or society as a whole?

TRANSPARENCY

Are the end-to-end processes and outputs of projects involving the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data fully transparent?

DATA AND AI MISUSE

Are there appropriate mitigations in place to protect sensitive data and reduce the likelihood that AI could be misused?

PUBLIC AWARENESS

Is there a clear communications plan to inform the public about how their sensitive data is being used to train AI models and/or how AI is being used to analyse their sensitive data?

OVERSIGHT, REGULATION AND ACCOUNTABILITY

Are there processes in place to ensure compliance with the necessary regulations; and are there clear lines of accountability if something goes wrong?

7/ Recommendations for future work

Based upon the findings outlined in this report, the following recommendations are made for future public dialogue on sensitive data and AI:

1/ Adopt a ‘funnel’ approach to knowledge development

To manage topic scope and drift, start with broad, introductory activities to draw out preconceived ideas about AI and gradually narrow to more focused discussions about AI trained on sensitive data. This “funnel” approach allows participants to build foundational understanding before tackling more specific topics, reducing overload of information and remaining firmly anchored on the focus of AI and sensitive data. Avoid trying to cover too much breadth of information and instead focus on specific use cases to hone understanding, continuously clarifying and reinforcing the scope of discussions.

2/ Embed sufficient time for learning and reflection

Given the complexity of the topics, public conversations about data and AI should allow sufficient time for participants to absorb information and reflect on discussions. This includes breaks during sessions, sufficient opportunities for Q&A, and structured reflection activities. A multi-stage process with multiple workshops also allows time for digestion and reflection, and workshops should be spaced over several days or weeks to support this, rather than together in a single block. Short, one-off sessions or single-day events are not recommended for public conversations on this topic, as they do not provide sufficient time to learn and contribute meaningfully.

3/ Engage in community settings

Future public involvement should prioritise meeting participants in spaces local to them, rather than expecting them to travel to distant or formal venues. Hosting workshops in community-based locations fosters trust, reduces perceived power imbalances and creates a sense of belonging. In addition, choosing meeting days and times to suit the needs and schedules of participants enables involvement alongside existing work, study and caring commitments. Pre-workshop materials should be publicly accessible and aim to portray a sense of comfort, approachability and friendliness while providing clear information about what to expect at the in-person events.

4/ Include a variety of interactive activities

Workshops should include diverse, hands-on activities that cater to different learning styles and keep participants actively engaged. Examples include collage or poster-making, scenario-based discussions, and movement-based exercises such as contributing ideas on sticky notes and flip charts around the room. These activities not only work to enhance understanding, but also encourage creativity, collaboration, relationship-building and fun. Presentations should be concise, broken into digestible segments, and paired with ample opportunity for Q&A to support participants in building understanding. While this is already good practice in public dialogue, participant feedback re-emphasised its importance when exploring such a technical, fast-moving topic.

5/ Illustrate concepts with real world examples

Complex concepts such as TREs and ML should be illustrated through practical, real-world examples. Demonstrations by researchers who have used them, and examples of AI models trained on sensitive data in use, could make abstract ideas more tangible and relatable. Visual aids, such as diagrams and infographics, should complement presentations to improve accessibility and engagement. This helps participants connect theoretical discussions to tangible, real-life scenarios, reinforcing understanding.

6/ Ensure consistency and accessibility of language

Terminology about AI in the context of sensitive data research should be consistent in conversations with the public. Creation of established plain language messaging, in close collaboration with members of the public, will help to support future conversations. Technical jargon should be avoided or clearly explained to support inclusivity and ensure all attendees, regardless of prior knowledge, can engage meaningfully with the content. Including both subject matter experts and public contributors involved in sensitive data and AI projects can be valuable for building trust and enabling informed discussions.

8/ Next steps

This pilot project has provided valuable learnings for future public conversations on sensitive data and AI. The responsible use of AI trained on sensitive data requires a proactive approach which prioritises trust and transparency while fostering ongoing dialogue with the public. This should not be a one-time effort, but a continuous process of learning, adapting and improving as technology and public expectations evolve.

This work has also highlighted important areas for further research with the public. The level of human involvement in AI expected by the public should be explored in more depth, particularly across different settings. There is also more exploration needed into what is considered AI 'misuse' from the public perspective, and what mitigations and regulations would make the public comfortable that AI trained on sensitive data is protected from misuse. This includes both technical and governance approaches to mitigating this risk, existing examples of which were not explored in detail with participants of this pilot project.

Furthermore, due to the current domination of healthcare-related examples of AI models trained on sensitive data across the sector, these workshops had a heavier focus on these examples than on other domains. Future work should seek to explore a greater variety of non-health examples with the public, as well as industry specific use cases.

DARE UK will be taking the findings of this work forward to inform a larger dialogue on the same topic with people from across all four nations of the UK, which will aim to set out more specific, actionable guidance about the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data. It will involve participants of this pilot project – who have expressed a keen interest in remaining involved – as advisors. Their input will be extremely valuable in helping to take forward the learnings of this pilot.

9/ Limitations

There were some limitations to this work, which offer important learnings for future conversations with the public on this and similar topics.

RECRUITMENT AND REPRESENTATION

Participants welcomed that there was a diverse group of people from the local community involved in the workshops. The demographic characteristics of participants, as outlined in Appendix 2, demonstrate diversity of age, ethnicity and socio-economic background and caring responsibilities. However, a majority of 74% of those who responded to the demographic survey identified as women, and 84% identified as heterosexual or straight. Future recruitment efforts should include targeted outreach to spaces and networks where people who identify as men or non-binary, and people from the LGBTQ+ community, are more likely to visit or engage with. This will help to ensure greater diversity of gender and sexuality among participants.

GEOGRAPHY AND SAMPLE SIZE

This was an exploratory piece of work with limited resources, and as such these workshops were limited to a single location and a relatively small sample size. Expanding future engagement to include larger numbers of participants across multiple geographical regions in all four nations of the UK is important for enabling greater representation of public views.

CONSISTENCY OF PARTICIPATION

Not all participants attended all the same sessions, with some individuals recruited later only joining the online induction and not the first workshop. While no clear divide emerged in subsequent sessions, this variation could have influenced the depth of shared understanding among participants.

SCOPE OF QUESTIONS

This was a pilot project with a primary objective of exploring how to have effective conversations about sensitive data and AI with people without existing understanding and awareness of the topic. The scope and depth of questions explored with participants was therefore limited, and future work should seek to explore answers to more specific questions via a deliberative process, with a view to producing clear and actionable guidance for the development and use of AI trained on sensitive data.

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11/ Appendices

Appendix 1: Workshop agenda

Workshop 1 Tuesday 21 October 2025	
Time	Item
10.00	Arrivals and refreshments/registration
10.30	Welcome
10.40	Co-creating a 'Ways of Working' poster
10.50	Introductions and icebreaker
11.00	Presentation and Q&A: What is sensitive data, and how is it safely and securely used for research? Elizabeth Waind, DARE UK
11.30	Break
11.40	Facilitated table activity: Exploring risks and benefits of using sensitive data in research - Participants discuss and place research uses cases on 'risk' versus 'benefit' scale - Feedback of key points from each table
12.15	Lunch
13.00	Full room discussion: What is Artificial Intelligence (AI)? - Using a timeline placed on the wall, participants discuss examples of when they use AI throughout an average day
13.15	Facilitated table discussion: Exploring benefits and concerns about AI
13.30	Presentation, video and Q&A: Developing AI models in Trusted Research Environments Professor Jim Smith, University of the West of England
13.55	Facilitated table discussion: Reflections from the presentation – exploring thoughts, views and concerns - Feedback of key points from each table
14.20	Wrap-up and reflections
14.30	Close

Online induction Monday 27 October 2025	
Time	Item
10.00	Welcome
10.05	Ways of working and icebreaker
10.20	Full room discussion: What is Artificial Intelligence (AI)? - Using a timeline placed on the wall, participants discuss examples of when they use AI throughout an average day
10.40	Presentation and Q&A: What is sensitive data, and how is it safely and securely used for research? Elizabeth Waind, DARE UK
11.00	Break
11.10	Presentation, video and Q&A: Developing AI models in Trusted Research Environments Elizabeth Waind, DARE UK
11.30	Full room discussion: Reflections from the presentation - Exploring thoughts, views and concerns
11.50	Wrap-up and reflections
12.00	Close

Appendix 1: Workshop agenda

Workshop 2 Tuesday 28 October 2025	
Time	Item
10.00	Arrivals and refreshments/registration
10.30	Welcome and recap
10.40	Table icebreaker
10.45	Presentation and Q&A: Enabling research with sensitive data on AI supercomputers Dr Martin O'Reilly, The Alan Turing Institute, and Antony Chuter, public contributor
11.10	Facilitated table discussion: Reflections from the presentation – exploring thoughts, views and concerns - Feedback of key points from each table
11.35	Break
11.50	Facilitated table activity: Exploring real-world examples of AI models trained on sensitive data - Each table looks at three examples and discusses their views, thoughts and concerns about each - Feedback of key points from each table
12.30	Lunch
13.15	Group table activity: Illustrating your views on the development and of use of AI trained on sensitive data - In groups, using materials provided (magazines, drawing materials) groups create a poster illustrating their views (e.g. do's and don'ts; key principles; hopes and concerns) - Posters presented back to the room
14.15	Wrap-up and reflections
14.30	Close

Workshop 3 Tuesday 4 November 2025	
Time	Item
10.00	Arrivals and refreshments/registration
10.30	Welcome and recap
10.45	Presentation: Revisiting the last workshops and key themes identified
10.55	Facilitated table discussion: Reflections and discussion on key themes identified
11.15	Break
11.30	Facilitated table activity: Reflections on language and terms - Each table works through stack of cards with terms or phrases and puts into green/amber/red based upon shared understanding - Feedback of key points from each table
12.00	Whole room activity: Capturing thoughts and views on the workshops - Participants use sticky notes to add their reflections on different aspects of the workshop process to boards placed around the room
12.15	Lunch
13.00	Facilitated table discussion: Reflective feedback on the workshop process - Feedback of key points from each table
13.40	Wrap-up
13.55	Optional: Photos and testimonials
14.30	Close

Appendix 2: Demographic characteristics of workshop participants

Of a total of 22 workshop participants, 19 responded to the anonymous demographic survey. The data below therefore represents the characteristics of the 19 participants who responded.

Demographic variable		# (%)
Age	Up to and including 24 years	1 (5.3%)
	25-34	1 (5.3%)
	35-44	7 (36.7%)
	45-54	6 (31.6%)
	55-64	2 (10.6%)
	65-74	2 (10.6%)
Disability	Yes	3 (15.8%)
	No	13 (68.4%)
	Prefer not to say	3 (15.8%)
Ethnicity	Asian or Asian British – Bangladeshi	2 (10.6%)
	Asian or Asian British – Chinese	1 (5.3%)
	Asian or Asian British – Pakistani	3 (15.8%)
	Black or Black British – African	2 (10.6%)
	Black or Black British – Caribbean	1 (5.3%)
	Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups - White and Black African	1 (5.3%)
	Any other mixed or multiple ethnic groups	1 (5.3%)
	White – English, Welsh, Scottish, Northern Irish or British	7 (36.7%)

Demographic variable		# (%)
Sex	Female	14 (73.7%)
	Male	5 (26.3%)
Gender	Woman	14 (73.7%)
	Man	4 (21%)
	Self-described gender	1 (5.3%)
Sexuality	Asexual	1 (5.3%)
	Bi/bisexual	1 (5.3%)
	Straight/heterosexual	16 (84.2%)
	Prefer not to say	1 (5.3%)
Caring responsibilities	None	3 (15.8%)
	Primary carer of a child or children (under 18)	6 (31.6%)
	Joint primary carer of a child or children (under 18)	5 (26.3%)
	Primary carer or assistant for a disabled adult (18 years or over)	1 (5.3%)
	Joint primary carer or assistant for a disabled adult (18 years or over)	1 (5.3%)
	Primary carer or assistant for an older person or people (65 and over)	1 (5.3%)
	I have caring responsibilities but prefer not to specify what they are	2 (10.6%)
	Prefer not to say	1 (5.3%)

Demographic variable		# (%)
Occupation of main household earner when you were 14	Clerical and intermediate occupations such as: secretary, personal assistant, call centre agent, clerical worker, nursery nurse.	2 (10.6%)
	Long-term unemployed (claimed Jobseeker's Allowance or earlier unemployment benefit for more than a year).	2 (10.6%)
	Modern professional & traditional professional occupations such as: teacher, nurse, physiotherapist, social worker, musician, police officer (sergeant or above), software designer, accountant, solicitor, medical practitioner, scientist, civil / mechanical engineer.	6 (31.6%)
	Other such as: retired, this question does not apply to me, I don't know.	1 (5.3%)
	Routine, semi-routine manual and service occupations such as: postal worker, machine operative, security guard, caretaker, farm worker, catering assistant, sales assistant, HGV driver, cleaner, porter, packer, labourer, waiter/waitress, bar staff.	3 (15.8%)
	Small business owners who employed less than 25 people such as: corner shop owners, small plumbing companies, retail shop owner, single restaurant or cafe owner, taxi owner, garage owner.	2 (10.6%)
	Technical and craft occupations such as: motor mechanic, plumber, printer, electrician, gardener, train driver.	2 (10.6%)

Appendix 3: Steering group members

Antony Chuter

TREvolution (Public Member)

Judith Fisher

TREvolution (University of Dundee)

Dr Gary Hickey

Independent Facilitator

Shayda Kashef

ADR UK (Administrative Data Research UK)

Samaira Khan

Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative (PEDRI)

Maisie McKenzie

DARE UK (Public Member)

Katie Porter (Co-Chair)

DARE UK

Elizabeth Waind (Co-Chair)

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